

ESTUDO DA ADSORÇÃO DOS CORANTES VIOLETA CRISTAL E VERDE MALAQUITA EM MATERIAL ZEOLÍTICO

ADSORPTION STUDY OF CRYSTAL VIOLET AND MALACHITE GREEN DYES IN ZEOLITIC MATERIAL

KLUNK, Marcos Antônio^{1*}; DASGUPTA, Sudipta²; DAS, Mohuli²; WANDER, Paulo Roberto¹; SHAH, Zeban³¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos, São Leopoldo, RS, Brazil² Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai 400076, India³ Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, RS, Brazil

* Autor correspondente
e-mail: marcosak@edu.unisinos.br

Received 14 July 2019; received in revised form 06 September 2019; accepted 26 September 2019

RESUMO

Violeta cristal e verde malaquita são corantes utilizados na indústria têxtil. Estes compostos orgânicos são agentes tóxicos capaz de poluir recursos hídricos, bem como destruir a biota existente neste local. A descoloração de efluentes têxteis sempre foi um problema mundial, mas tem sido acentuada ao longo do tempo com a crescente operação em grande escala e mudanças na origem do uso de corantes. A descoloração das águas residuais pode ser conseguida removendo fisicamente o corante da água ou destruindo o seu grupo cromóforo. A adsorção é referida como um dos métodos mais eficientes e viáveis para descolorir um efluente. As peneiras moleculares (zeólitas) tem se mostrado uma alternativa eficiente na descoloração dos efluentes têxteis quando comparados a outros processos na indústria. A sodalita é uma zeólita que apresentar a capacidade de adsorver os grupos funcionais azo, relacionados a cor. O foco principal deste trabalho é utilizar a sodalita no processo de descoloração de uma solução sintética de violeta cristal e verde malaquita. Os experimentos foram realizados variando-se os tempos de contato entre o material zeolítico e as soluções sintética dos corantes. Os resultados nos revelaram que ambos os corantes sofreram um processo de descoloração. Conforme as análises, tempos maiores de contato (12, 24, 48 e 72 horas) com a sodalita mostra-se mais eficiente na remoção da cor. Um fator decisivo neste processo é a maior razão Si/Al (2.5) de sodalita que potencializa o processo e eficiência dos experimentos.

Palavras-chave: Indústria Têxtil, Impactos Ambientais, Sodalita, Descoloração, Grupo Cromóforo

ABSTRACT

Violet crystal and malachite green are dyes used in the textile industry. These organic compounds are toxic agents capable of polluting water resources as well as destroying the existing biota in this location. The decolorization of textile effluents has always been a global problem, but it has accentuated over time with increasing scale operation and changes in the origin of the dyes used. Decolorization of wastewater achieved by physically removing the dye from the water or by destroying its chromophore group. Adsorption is referred to as one of the most efficient and feasible methods for discoloring an effluent. Molecular sieves (zeolites) showed to be an efficient alternative in the discoloration of textile effluents when compared to other processes in the industry. Sodalite is a zeolite that has the ability to adsorb the azo functional groups related to color. The focus of this work is to use sodalite in the process of discoloration of a synthetic solution of crystal violet and malachite green. The experiments performed by varying the contact times between the zeolitic material and the synthetic solutions of the dyes. The results revealed that both dyes had a decolorization process. According to analyzes, greater times of contact (12, 24, 48, and 72 hours) with sodalite is more efficient in the removal color. A decisive factor in this process is the higher Si/Al ratio (2.5) of sodalite that potentiates the process and efficiency of the experiments.

Keywords: Textile Industry, Environmental Impacts, Sodalite, Decolorization, Chromophore Group.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pollution in aquatic systems is caused by industrial activity (Klunk *et al.*, 2017). The chemical contaminants present in the water resources are textile dyes, surfactants, and heavy metals (Klunk *et al.*, 2019a; Kumar *et al.*, 2017). These toxic agents cause the destruction of biota and changes in natural landscapes, as well as the destruction of water for human consumption (Humelnicu *et al.*, 2017). The great cause of pollution in water the textile dyes (Klunk *et al.*, 2019b). The main route of entry of the dyes into the environment is through the release of waste water. About 10 to 15 % of all dyes are directly discarded as wastewater in the dyeing process (Francis *et al.*, 2017). The first effect to be detected after illegal dumping is its aesthetic nature. At the concentration of 1 mg/L of dye, it is already enough to give color to the water resource (Chawla *et al.*, 2017). This situation makes it impossible to use water for recreational purposes and affects the natural balance of plants and other living things in the environment (Kooli *et al.*, 2015).

According to with “Ecological and Toxicological Association of Dyes and Organic Pigment Manufacturers”, the majority of dyes (98 %) present lethal concentration values (LC50) in fish larger than 1 mg/L (Forgacs *et al.*, 2004). The decolorization of textile effluents has always been a global problem, but it has been accentuated over time with increasing scale operation and changes in the origin of the dyes used (Abdulrahman, 2014). As consumers become more demanding with the product (brightness, color, resistance to washing and light), the colorants become less receptive to degradation and resistant to moderate oxidation conditions (Koshy and Singh, 2016). Decolorization of wastewater can be achieved by physically removing the dye from the water or by destroying its chromophore group. Adsorption is referred to as one of the most efficient and feasible methods for discoloring an effluent (Ali, 2012; Al-Anber and Al-Anber, 2008). It is advantageous in terms of the possibility of re-use of process water, initial cost, ease of operation and insensitivity to toxic substances (Fraga *et al.*, 2014; Klunk *et al.*, 2012; Ali *et al.*, 2012; Atun *et al.*, 2011). The present work has the objective of studying the adsorption of the dye crystal violet (CV) and malachite green (MG) using molecular sieves (zeolites) as adsorbent material. For this study, standard solutions of the dyes (50 mg/L) were prepared which were contacted with the zeolitic material in the periods of 1 - 72 hours. Sodalite (zeolite) was used as adsorbent material in four Si/Al ratios (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5). These ratios

allow identifying the best adsorption condition of the dyes under study. At the end of the experiments, the products of decolorization system were analyzed by Ultraviolet - Visible Spectroscopy (UV-VIS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) e High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), to verify the efficiency of the adsorbent in the removal of the color from the textile effluent.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Molecular Sieves

Molecular sieves, also called zeolites, are hydrated aluminosilicates mineral of alkali metals and alkaline earths (mainly sodium, potassium, and magnesium) (Ali, 2012; Ali and Gupta, 2007). According to the International Association of Mineralogy, a zeolitic mineral is a crystalline substance with a structure characterized by structures in continuous three-dimensional crystalline networks of tetrahedral composed of four atoms of oxygen around a cation (SiO_4 , AlO_4), so that each oxygen is cut between two tetrahedral (Atun *et al.*, 2011). The zeolites, in general, have structures in continuous three-dimensional crystalline networks, composed of tetrahedral of type MO_4 (being, $\text{M} = \text{Si}, \text{Al}, \text{Be}, \text{Ge}, \text{Fe}, \text{P}, \text{Co}$) (Belviso *et al.*, 2013). Due to its properties, such as the cation exchange capacity, its high surface area, its acid centers, the size of its channels and cavities and its selectivity of form 40, the natural zeolites are of great interest for the study (Koshy and Singh, 2016; Zhou *et al.*, 2014; Xie *et al.*, 2014). It should be noted that the low cost of natural zeolites has provided and stimulated the development of cheaper treatment systems (Chang and Shih, 2000; Blanchard *et al.*, 1984).

Despite having a very varied chemical composition, zeolites are usually classified according to their structure. For this study, the sodalite zeolite was synthesized and used as adsorbent material of textile dyes. Sodalite (SOD) ($\text{Na}_8\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{24}\text{Cl}_2$) was first discovered by Thomson in 1811, and after a few years in 1930, its structure was clarified by Paulling (Smith *et al.*, 2008; Smith, 2000). From this discovery, different synthesis processes were carried out to produce sodalite with the most varied compositions. The arrangement of this mineral is entirely formed by uniform truncated octahedral polyhedral, called sodalite or β -cage (Ding *et al.*, 2010; Nakano and Nozue, 2007; Bibb and Dale, 1985). Then, the α cages (supercages) with the inside diameter of

~11 Å are formed among the β cages. The α cages are connected by the sharing of the 8-membered ring with each other and also arrayed in a simple cubic structure. The lattice constant is 12.3 Å (Nakano and Nozue, 2007; Bibb and Dale, 1985).

2.2. Textile Dyes

Dyes are classified as anionic (acid dyes, direct and reactive), cationic (basic dyes) and nonionic (dispersive dyes) (Humelnicu *et al.*, 2017). The cationic dyes (referring to this work) present a characteristic behavior according to their concentration in solution (Almasian *et al.*, 2015). The dye molecules can bind to form molecular dimers, or even higher trimers and aggregates of the dyes (Alver *et al.*, 2012; Liu and Chiou, 2005).

In the experiments, were used the aqueous solutions of the CV and MG. The properties of the CV is cationic classification, with molecular formula $C_{25}H_{30}N_3Cl$, molecular weight 407.99 g/mol, and visible region exhibit the main peak with a maximum absorbance at λ_{max} at 591 nm. The retention time in HPLC is 10.2 min (Al-Kadhemy and Abaas, 2012; Alsharuee, 2012). Therefore, for the dye MG, also follows in the same classification of cationic, with molecular formula $C_{23}H_{25}N_2Cl$, molecular weight 364.91 g/mol and visible region exhibit the main peak with a maximum absorbance at λ_{max} at 620 nm. The retention time in HPLC is 4.3 min (Sartape *et al.*, 2017; Hameed and El-Khaiary, 2008).

2.3. Synthesis of the zeolitic material

The synthesis of zeolitic material (sodalite) was developed according to the studies of Henmi (1987). Sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by dissolving 80 g of NaOH in 1 L of distilled water. In order to obtain the zeolites with Si/Al ratio 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 was used as an aluminum solution, by dissolving the metakaolin ($Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2$). For the Si source, biomass residue from pyrolysis experiments was used (Klunk *et al.*, 2017b; Klunk *et al.*, 2018a; Ruoso *et al.*, 2019; Cataluña *et al.*, 2018; Caetano *et al.*, 2018; Caetano *et al.*, 2015a; Caetano *et al.*, 2015b). The gel was then oven-dried at 90 °C for 24 hours. In this process, sodalite acts as an ionic adsorbent agent enable of decolorization from textile industry effluents (Klunk *et al.*, 2019c).

In environmental terms, the use of biomass contributes to the low emissions of carbon dioxide

(CO₂) (Klunk *et al.*, 2018b; Cataluña *et al.*, 2017; Caetano *et al.*, 2015c; Caetano *et al.*, 2017). These low carbon dioxide emissions can be predicted by geochemical modeling (Klunk *et al.*, 2015; Klunk *et al.*, 2018c; Klunk *et al.*, 2019d; Ponomarev *et al.*, 2017).

2.4. Synthesis of the zeolitic material

In order to simulate dye contaminated effluent, was used as an aqueous solution of CV and MG (MERCK™) (Cooper, 1993). Dyes concentrations were determined by UV-visible spectrophotometry at wavelengths of 591 and 620 nm. An amount of 100 mg of adsorbent (sodalite) was placed in contact with 25 ml of a solution of adsorbate (CV and MG) at a concentration of 50 mg/L under constant stirring at 150 rpm for 24 hours (De Gisi *et al.*, 2016). After the contact time, the suspensions were centrifuged for 30 minutes at 2000 rpm, and an aliquot of the supernatant was extracted for determination of the final concentration of the dyes (Qu *et al.*, 2013).

In order to determination CV and MG color removal, 10 mL aliquots of the dyes were sampled at different periods (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 12, 24, 48 and 72 h) with 50 g of the zeolitic material (Sodalite) in different ratio Si/Al (1.0; 1.5; 2.0 and 2.5) (Klunk *et al.*, 2019c). The aqueous solution was examined by UV-Visible spectrophotometry (Ultra-Fast Scan UV-1900 - SHIMADZU™), FTIR (IRAffinity-1S - SHIMADZU™) and HPLC (LC-20A Prominence - SHIMADZU™).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Response adsorption of CV and MG dyes in zeolitic material

In the present study, in order to follow the molecular sieve dye decolorization process, were used some analytical techniques such as UV-Vis spectroscopy, HPLC, and FTIR spectroscopy.

3.1.1. Ultraviolet - Visible Spectroscopy (UV-VIS)

UV-Vis spectroscopy is the primary technique to determine dye decolorization (Sartape *et al.*, 2017). In Figure 1, the spectra of CV and MG at a concentration of 50 mg/L in visible region exhibit the main peak with a maximum absorbance at λ_{max} at 591 nm and 620 nm

respectively (De Gisi *et al.*, 2016; Qu *et al.*, 2013). The results of the UV-Visible spectra showed that peaks at λ_{\max} reached at 0 h (FZ – free zeolite) decreased significantly until 72 h. The most efficient sodalite ratio for dye discoloration is 2.5 for both CV and MG. For the Si/Al ratio 1.0, the decolorization became less useful for the samples that remained for 72 hours in contact with the adsorbent.

3.1.2. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

After adsorption with molecular sieve for 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 12, 24, 48 and 72 hours, the intermediates in the aqueous CV and MG solutions were extracted and analyzed via HPLC. In Figure 2, the peak at the retention time of 10.2 and 4.3 min was identified as CV and MG respectively (Cao *et al.*, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2016; Xie *et al.*, 2013; Ayed *et al.*, 2009; Andersen *et al.*, 2009). The extracted sample after adsorption shows that decolorization is increasing according to the ratios of Si/Al increase. These values agree when comparing the results of UV-Vis spectroscopy.

3.1.3. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR has widely used as a proper technique for investigation of dyes decolorizations experiments. In dyes decolorization studies, FTIR spectrum enables the determination of type interactions that occur within azo dyes containing different functional groups. Taking this into account, the FTIR spectroscopy used the region of 4500-500 cm^{-1} to investigate the decolorization process, and the results were shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 to CV and MG respectively. According to the FTIR spectra, the assignments of the primary infrared bands obtained with each dye at free zeolite (FZ) and 72 h in contact with the adsorbent material in two different Si/Al ratios (1.0 and 2.5). The FTIR spectroscopy from CV have peaks at 3413 – 2921 cm^{-1} indicates C-H asymmetric stretching and free $-\text{NH}_2$ group showed amide antisymmetric stretching vibration (Bevilacqua and Busca, 2002). Also, the peak at 2344 cm^{-1} corresponding to a symmetric and asymmetric stretching of the tertiary amine salt. The results showed remarkable variations in ranged from 1591 - 520 cm^{-1} to CV and 1650 – 545 cm^{-1} to MG (Ayed *et al.*, 2009). In 1591 cm^{-1}

corresponding to the C=C stretching of the benzene ring. The intensity variations of 1483 cm^{-1} are to six-member ring carbon-carbon vibrations and indicate a sideways ring stretch absorbs $=\text{CH}_2$. In 1361 cm^{-1} peak for the C–N stretch of aromatic tertiary amine (Akyuz and Akyuz, 2006). At 1172 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C–N stretching vibrations (Al-Kadhemy *et al.*, 2013). The peaks at 941, 831, 722 cm^{-1} correspond to symmetric out of plane bending of the ring hydrogens. The bands at 520 cm^{-1} are due to Si–O–Al (octahedral) from zeolitic material (Tyagi *et al.*, 2006).

The FTIR spectroscopy from MG have peaks at 3435 cm^{-1} indicates $-\text{NH}_2$ group showed amide antisymmetric stretching vibration (Barapatre *et al.*, 2017; Vijayalakshmidivi and Muthukumar, 2013; Nishioka, 1976). The peaks at 1650 – 1400 cm^{-1} is C=C aromatic ring and C–N stretch aromatic tertiary amine. Also, the peaks at 1190 and 1125 cm^{-1} are for aromatic C–N stretching vibrations of aliphatic amine (Saravanakumar and Kathiresan, 2014). Eventually, the peak at 620 cm^{-1} indicates aromatic amines. Bands at 545 cm^{-1} were related to the internal asymmetric stretching vibration of Si-O-Si or Si-O-Al were characteristic of Sodalite structure (Cheriaa *et al.*, 2012). Among them, the band at 545 cm^{-1} is related to a structure of the double five-membered rings of the pintails zeolites (Coates, 2000).

The changes in intensity variations for the dyes decolorization experiments are related to the adsorption capacity of the zeolitic as molecular sieves. According to the FTIR spectra, there was the formation of new functional groups when compared to the sample without zeolite (free zeolite). What occurred was a decrease in the intensity of the peaks. Again, the results can be compared with the other techniques used in this study, showing the same behavior.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The sodalite can be efficiently utilized as adsorbent for the removal of dyes (CV and MG) from aqueous solutions. In this context, the Si/Al ratios are responsible for the efficiency of the process. It was possible to identify that in the 2.5 ratios, the molecular sieve shows to be more active to adsorb both dyes (CV and MG). Soon for a reason 1.0, the process did not show us very efficiently. This discrepancy lies in the cation exchange capacity of the dyes. Thus, a low Si/Al ratio makes the molecular sieve less susceptible to the azo groups in the dye molecules. It is evident that for the three techniques used in this

process of decolorization of textile dyes, the behavior of the adsorbate has the ability to retain the color related functional groups.

The zeolite used to removal the color of a textile effluent can be more efficient in the ratio Si/Al 2.5. Nevertheless, the concentration of the synthetic solution of an effluent containing CV and MG has its importance, since often the industries do a process of dilution, being able to impact in the capacity of retention of the molecular sieve.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Brazilian agencies CNPq (National Council of Technological and Scientific Development – Brasília, DF, Brazil), CAPES (Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel) for the research funding, and the generous assistance of all the people from the company who granted us access to their database and perception information.

6. REFERENCES

1. Klunk, M. A., Ponomarev, A. A., Dasgupta, S., Das, M. Arsenic Speciation in Groundwater using the Softwares PHREEQC, GWB, and GEODELING. *Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry*. **2017a**, 25, 30-35.
2. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Das, M., Wander, P. R. Computer Codes of Geochemical Modeling used to Water-Rock Interaction Simple and Complex Systems. *Periódico Tchê Química*. **2019a**, 16(32), 108-118.
3. Kumar, M. A., Harthy, D. K., Kumar, V. V., Balashri, K. G., Seenuvasan, M., Anuradha, D., Sivanessand, S. Detoxification of a triphenylmethane textile colorant using acclimated cells of *Bacillus mannanilyticus* strain AVS. *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy*. **2017**, 36(2), 394–403.
4. Humelnicu, I., Băiceanu, A., Ignat, M. -E., Dulman, V. The removal of Basic Blue 41 textile dye from aqueous solution by adsorption onto natural zeolitic tuff: Kinetics and thermodynamics. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*. **2017**, 105, 274–287.
5. Klunk, M. A., Shah, Z., Wander, P. R. Use of Montmorillonite Clay for Adsorption Malachite Green Dye. *Periódico Tchê Química*. **2019b**, 16(32), 279-286.
6. Francis, S., Joseph, S., Koshy, E. P., Mathew, B. Green synthesis and characterization of gold and silver nanoparticles using *Mussaenda glabrata* leaf extract and their environmental applications to dye degradation. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. **2017**, 24(21), 17347–17357.
7. Chawla, S., Uppal, H., Yadav, M., Bahadur, N., Singh, N. Zinc peroxide nanomaterial as an adsorbent for removal of Congo red dye from waste water. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*. **2017**, 135, 68–74.
8. Kooli, F., Liu, Y., Al-Faze, R., Al Suhaimi, A. Effect of acid activation of Saudi local clay mineral on removal properties of basic blue 41 from an aqueous solution. *Applied Clay Science*. **2015**, 116-117, 23–30.
9. Forgacs, E., Cserháti, T., Oros, G. Removal of synthetic dyes from wastewaters: a review. *Environment International*. **2004**, 30(7), 953–971.
10. Abdulrahman G. Adsorption of Acid Dyes from Wastewater on Saudi Bentonite Clay. *Trends in Applied Sciences Research*. **2014**, 9, 557-573.
11. Koshy, N., Singh, D. N. Fly ash zeolites for water treatment applications. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*. **2016**, 4(2), 1460–1472.
12. Ali, I. New Generation Adsorbents for Water Treatment. *Chemical Reviews*. **2012**, 112(10), 5073–5091.
13. Al-Anber, M., Al-Anber, Z. A. Utilization of natural zeolite as ion-exchange and sorbent material in the removal of iron. *Desalination*. **2008**, 225(1-3), 70–81.
14. Fraga, A., Klunk, M. A., Oliveira, A., Furtado, G., Knornschild, G. H., Dick, L. F. P. Soil corrosion of the AISI1020 steel buried near electrical power transmission line towers. *Materials Research-Ibero-american Journal of Materials*. **2014**, 17, 1637-1643.
15. Klunk, M. A., Oliveira, A., Furtado, G., Knornschild, G. H., Dick, L. F. P. Study of the Corrosion of Buried Steel Grids of Electrical Power Transmission Towers. *ECS Transactions*. **2012**, 43, 23-27.
16. Ali, I., Asim, M., Khan, T. A. Low cost adsorbents for the removal of organic pollutants from wastewater. *Journal of Environmental Management*. **2012**, 113, 170–183.
17. Atun, G., Hisarlı, G., Kurtoğlu, A. E., Ayar,

- N. A comparison of basic dye adsorption onto zeolitic materials synthesized from fly ash. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. **2011**, 187(1-3), 562–573.
18. Ali, I., Gupta, V. K. Advances in water treatment by adsorption technology. *Nature Protocols*. **2007**, 1(6), 2661–2667.
 19. Belviso, C., Cavalcante, F., Fiore, S. Ultrasonic waves induce rapid zeolite synthesis in a seawater solution. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*. **2013**, 20(1), 32–36.
 20. Zhou, L., Chen, Y. -L., Zhang, X. -H., Tian, F. -M., Zu, Z. -N. Zeolites developed from mixed alkali modified coal fly ash for adsorption of volatile organic compounds. *Materials Letters*. **2014**, 119, 140–142.
 21. Xie, J., Wang, Z., Wu, D., Kong, H. Synthesis and properties of zeolite/hydrated iron oxide composite from coal fly ash as an efficient adsorbent to simultaneously retain cationic and anionic pollutants from water. *Fuel*. **2014**, 116, 71–76.
 22. Chang, H. -L., Shih, W. -H. Synthesis of Zeolites A and X from Fly Ashes and Their Ion-Exchange Behavior with Cobalt Ions. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. **2000**, 39(11), 4185–4191.
 23. Blanchard, G., Maunaye, M., Martin, G. Removal of heavy metals from waters by means of natural zeolites. *Water Research*. **1984**, 18(12), 1501–1507.
 24. Smith, P., Wingate, C., Silva, L. Mobility of included soda in sodalite. In: Proceedings of the 8th International Alumina Quality Workshop, **2008**.
 25. Smith, J. V. Microporous and other Framework Materials with Zeolite-type Structures, Springer, New York, **2000**.
 26. Ding L., Yang H., Rahimi P., Omotoso O., Friesen W., Fairbridge C., Shi Y., Siauw, Ng. Solid transformation of zeolite NaA to sodalite. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*. **2010**, 130, 303–308.
 27. Nakano, T., Nozue, Y. Orbital degeneracy and magnetic properties of potassium clusters incorporated into nanoporous crystals of zeolite A. *Journal of Computational Methods in Sciences and Engineering*. **2007**, 443–462.
 28. Bibby, D. M., Dale, M. P. Synthesis of silica-sodalite from non-aqueous systems. *Nature*. **1985**, 317, 157-158.
 29. Almasian, A., Parvinzadeh Gashti, M., Olya, M. E., Chizari Fard, G. Poly(acrylic acid)-zeolite nanocomposites for dye removal from single and binary systems. *Desalination and Water Treatment*. **2015**, 1-19.
 30. Alver, E., Metin, A.Ü. Anionic dye removal from aqueous solutions using modified zeolite: Adsorption kinetics and isotherm studies. *Chemical Engineering Journal*. **2012**, 200-202, 59–67.
 31. Liu, H. -L., Chiou, Y. -R. Optimal decolorization efficiency of Reactive Red 239 by UV/TiO₂ photocatalytic process coupled with response surface methodology. *Chemical Engineering Journal*. **2005**, 112(1-3), 173–179.
 32. Al-Kadhemy M. F. H., Abaas W.H. Absorption spectrum of Crystal Violet in Chloroform solution and doped PMMA thin films. *Atti Della Fondazione Giorgio Ronchi*. **2012**, 3, 359-367.
 33. Alsharuee I. F. Theoretical model to study the effect of concentration on the absorption spectrum of crystal violet in methanol using asymmetric double sigmoid. *Atti Della Fondazione Giorgio Ronchi*. **2012**, 1, 5-14.
 34. Hameed, B. H., El-Khaiary, M. I. Malachite green adsorption by rattan sawdust: Isotherm, kinetic, and mechanism modeling. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. **2008**, 159(2-3), 574–579.
 35. Henmi, T. Synthesis of hydroxy-sodalite (“zeolite”) from waste coal ash. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*. **1987**, 33(3), 517-521.
 36. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Das, M. Influence of Fast Pyrolysis with Temperature on Gas, Char and Bio-oil Production. *Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry*. **2017b**, 25, 1-11.
 37. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Das, M. Slow Pyrolysis of Rice Straw: Analysis of Biochar, Bio-Oil, and Gas. *Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry*. **2018a**, 26, 17-25.
 38. Ruoso, F. S., Bittencourt, L. C., Sudati, L. U., Klunk, M. A., Caetano, N. R. New Parameters for the Forest Biomass Waste Ecofirewood Manufacturing Process Optimization. *Periódico Tchê Química*. **2019**, 16(32), 560-571.
 39. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Nunes, B. V. G., Wander, P. R. Synthesis of Sodalite Zeolite to Treatment of Textile Effluents. *Periódico Tchê Química*. **2019c**, 16, 778-783.
 40. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Das, M., Shah, Z. System of Adsorption of CO₂ in

- Coalbed. *Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry*. **2018b**, 26, 2-9.
41. Cataluña, R., Shah, Z., Venturi, V., Caetano, N. R., Da Silva, B. P., Azevedo, C. M. N., Da Silva, R., Suarez, P. A. Z., Oliveira, L. P. Production process of di-amyl ether and its use as an additive in the formulation of aviation fuels. *Fuel*. **2018**, 228, 226-233.
 42. Caetano, N. R., Venturini, M. S., Centeno, F. R., Lemmertz, C. K., Kyprianidis, K. G. Assessment of mathematical models for prediction of thermal radiation heat loss from laminar and turbulent jet non-premixed flames. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress*. **2018**, 7, 241–247.
 43. Caetano, N. R., Stapasolla, T. Z., Peng, F. B., Schneider, P. S., Pereira, F. M., Vielmo, H. A. Diffusion Flame Stability of Low Calorific Fuels. *Defect and Diffusion Forum*. **2015a**, 362, 29-37.
 44. Caetano, N. R., Cataluña, R., Vielmo, H. A. Analysis of the Effect on the Mechanical Injection Engine Using Doped Diesel Fuel by Ethanol and Bio-Oil. *International Review of Mechanical Engineering*. **2015b**, 9(2), 124-128.
 45. Cataluña, R., Shah, Z., Pelisson, L., Caetano, N. R., Da Silva, R., Azevedo, C., Biodiesel Glycerides from the Soybean Ethylic Route Incomplete Conversion on the Diesel Engines Combustion Process. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*. **2017**, 00, 1-8.
 46. Caetano, N. R., Soares, D., Nunes, R. P., Pereira, F. M., Schneider, P. S., Vielmo, H. A., van der Laan, F. T. A comparison of experimental results of soot production in laminar premixed flames. *Open Engineering*. **2015c**, 5, 213–219.
 47. Caetano, N. R.; Silva, B. P. Technical and Economic Viability for the Briquettes Manufacture. *Defect and Diffusion Forum*. **2017**, 380, 218-226.
 48. Klunk, M. A., Damiani, L. H., Feller, G., Rey, M. F., Conceição, R. V., Abel, M., De Ros, L. F. Geochemical modeling of diagenetic reactions in Snorre Field reservoir sandstones: a comparative study of computer codes. *Brazilian Journal of Geology*. **2015**, 45, 29-40.
 49. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Conceição, R. V. Computerized geochemical modeling of burial diagenesis of the Eocene turbidite reservoir elements: Urucutuca Formation, Espírito Santo Basin, southeastern Brazil passive margin. *Journal of Palaeogeography*. **2018c**, 7, 12-26.
 50. Klunk, M. A., Dasgupta, S., Schropfer, S. B., Nunes, B. V. G., Wander, P. R. Comparative Study of Geochemical Speciation Modeling Using GEODELING Software. *Periódico Tchê Química*. **2019d**, 16(31), 816-822.
 51. Ponomarev, A. A., Bubnova, A. V., Klunk, M. A. The Use of X-Ray Microtomography to Assess Changes in the Voids Structure of Rocks. *Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry*. **2017**, 25, 12-16.
 52. Cooper, P., Removing colour from dye house wastewater – a critical review of technology available. *Journal of the Society of Dyers and Colourists*. **1993**, 109, 97-100.
 53. De Gisi, S., Lofrano, G., Grassi, M., Notarnicola, M. Characteristics and adsorption capacities of low-cost sorbents for wastewater treatment: A review. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*. **2016**, 9, 10-40.
 54. Qu, X., Alvarez, P. J., and Li, Q. Applications of nanotechnology in water and wastewater treatment. *Water Research*. **2013**, 47, 3931-3946.
 55. Sartape, A. S., Mandhare, A. M., Jadhav, V. V., Raut, P. D., Anuse, M. A., Kolekar, S. S. Removal of malachite green dye from aqueous solution with adsorption technique using Limonia acidissima (wood apple) shell as low cost adsorbent. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*. **2017**, 10, S3229–S3238.
 56. Cao, D. -J., Wang, J. -J., Zhang, Q., Wen, Y. -Z., Dong, B., Liu, R. -J., Geng, G. Biodegradation of triphenylmethane dye crystal violet by *Cedecea davisae*. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*. **2019**, 210, 9-13.
 57. Yang, X., Zheng, J., Lu, Y., Jia, R. Degradation and detoxification of the triphenylmethane dye malachite green catalyzed by crude manganese peroxidase from *Irpex lacteus* F17. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. **2016**, 23(10), 9585–9597.
 58. Xie, J., Peng, T., Chen, D. -D., Zhang, Q. -J., Wang, G. -M., Wang, X., Deng, J. Determination of malachite green, crystal violet and their leuco-metabolites in fish by HPLC–VIS detection after immunoaffinity column clean-up. *Journal of Chromatography B*. **2013**, 913-914, 123–128.

59. Ayed, L., Cheriaa, J., Laadhari, N., Cheref, A., Bakhrouf, A. Biodegradation of crystal violet by an isolated *Bacillus* sp. *Annals of Microbiology*. **2009**, 59(2), 267–272.
60. Andersen, W. C., Turnipseed, S. B., Karbiwnyk, C. M., Lee, R. H., Clark, S. B., Rowe, W. D., Miller, K. E. Multiresidue method for the triphenylmethane dyes in fish: Malachite green, crystal (gentian) violet, and brilliant green. *Analytica Chimica Acta*. **2009**, 637(1-2), 279–289.
61. Bevilacqua M., Busca G. A study of the localization and accessibility of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites of H-mordenite through the FT-IR spectroscopy of adsorbed branched nitriles. *Catalysis Communications*. **2002**, 3, 497-502.
62. Akyuz S., Akyuz T. FT-IR spectroscopic investigations of adsorption of 2-, 3- and 4-pyridinecarboxamide on montmorillonite and saponite from Anatolia. *Vibrational Spectroscopy*. **2006**, 42, 387-391.
63. Al-Kadhemy, M. F. H., Abaas, W. H., Fakher, I. The Effect of Gamma Radiation on the FTIR Spectrum of Crystal Violet Doped Polystyrene Films. *Caspian Journal of Applied Sciences Research*. **2013**, 2(7), 11-17.
64. Tyagi B., Chudasama C., Jasra D. R. V. Determination of structural modification in acid activated montmorillonite clay by FT-IR spectroscopy. *Spectrochimica Acta A*. **2006**, 64, 273–278.
65. Barapatre, A., Aadil, K. R., Jha, H. Biodegradation of Malachite Green by the Ligninolytic Fungus *Aspergillus flavus*. *CLEAN - Soil, Air, Water*. **2017**, 45(4), 1600045, 1-12.
66. Vijayalakshmi, S. R., Muthukumar, K. Biodegradation of malachite green by *Ochrobactrum* sp. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*. **2013**, 30(2), 429–437.
67. Nishioka, N. S. Thesis, University of California, Berkeley, CA, **1976**.
68. Saravanakumar, K., Kathiresan, K. Bioremoval of the synthetic dye malachite green by marine *Trichoderma* sp. *SpringerPlus*. **2014**, 3(1), 631.
69. Cheriaa, J., Khairredine, M., Rouabhia, M., Bakhrouf, A. Removal of Triphenylmethane Dyes by Bacterial Consortium. *The Scientific World Journal*. **2012**, 1–9.
70. Coates, J. Interpretation of infrared spectra. A practical approach. In *Encyclopedia of Analytical Chemistry*. Meyers, R.A. Ed., pp. 10815–10837, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester, UK, **2000**.

Figure 1: UV-vis spectrum of CV and MG. *FZ: Free-Zeolite

Figure 2: Chromatogram of the CV and MG of decolorization analyzed by HPLC. *FZ: Free-Zeolite

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of CV. *FZ: Free-Zeolite

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of MG. *FZ: Free-Zeolite